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PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR ORGANIZING MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING AND INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEMS IN FISHERY CLUSTERS

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Abstract. The article examines priority directions for organizing management accounting and internal control systems in fishery clusters. The research is based on the 2019–2024 practice of fishery clusters within the “O‘zbekbaliqsanoat” Association. The author developed proposals in three main areas: (1) organizational and methodological aspects of the management accounting policy; (2) a mixed transfer pricing model based either on market price or on cost plus a 15–25% margin; and (3) a segment reporting template for five operating segments in accordance with IFRS 8 requirements. In addition, five components of the internal control system for fishery clusters are proposed based on the COSO Internal Control — Integrated Framework. The research results have practical significance for improving the efficiency, transparency, and controllability of fishery clusters.

Keywords: fishery clusters, management accounting, internal control, COSO, transfer pricing, segment reporting, IFRS 8, agroclusters, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada baliqchilik klasterlarida boshqaruv hisobi va ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil etishning ustuvor yo‘nalishlari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda «O‘zbekbaliqsanoat» uyushmasi tarkibidagi baliqchilik klasterlarining 2019–2024-yillardagi amaliyoti o‘rganildi. Muallif tomonidan uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi: (1) boshqaruv hisobi bo‘yicha “Hisob siyosati”ning tashkiliy-uslubiy jihatlari; (2) transfert bahoni shakllantirishning aralash modeli — bozor narxi asosida yoki tannarxga 15–25 foizlik marja qo‘shish asosida; (3) IFRS 8 talablariga mos ravishda beshta operatsion segment bo‘yicha segmentar hisobot shakli. Shu bilan birga, COSO Internal Control — Integrated Framework asosida baliqchilik klasterlari uchun ichki nazorat tizimining beshta komponenti taklif etildi. Tadqiqot natijalari baliqchilik klasterlari samaradorligi, shaffofligi va boshqaruvchanligini oshirishda amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so‘zlar: baliqchilik klasterlari, boshqaruv hisobi, ichki nazorat, COSO, transfert baho, segmentar hisobot, IFRS 8, agroklasteralar, O‘zbekiston.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются приоритетные направления организации управленческого учёта и системы внутреннего контроля в рыболовческих кластерах. Исследование основано на практике рыболовческих кластеров ассоциации «O‘zbekbaliqsanoat» за 2019–2024 годы. Автором разработаны предложения по трём основным направлениям: (1) организационно-методологические аспекты управленческой учётной политики; (2) смешанная модель формирования трансфертных цен на основе рыночной цены либо себестоимости с добавлением маржи 15–25%; (3) форма сегментарной отчётности по пяти операционным сегментам в соответствии с требованиями IFRS 8. Кроме того, на основе COSO Internal Control — Integrated Framework предложены пять компонентов системы внутреннего контроля для рыболовческих кластеров. Результаты исследования имеют практическое значение для повышения эффективности, прозрачности и управляемости рыболовческих кластеров.

Ключевые слова: рыболовческие кластеры, управленческий учёт, внутренний контроль, COSO, трансфертные цены, сегментарная отчётность, IFRS 8, агрокластеры, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The strategy for clustering the agricultural sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan was established within the framework of the Action Strategy approved by Presidential Decree No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 [3]. This policy is being actively implemented in the fishery sector. Between 2017 and 2024, fish production increased from 83.9 thousand tons to 199.4 thousand tons [1], while the number of full-cycle fishery clusters grew from 5 to 13 [2].

Clusters are organizational structures that unite business entities engaged in the production, storage,

processing, transportation, and sale of agricultural products. The specific feature of a fishery cluster lies in its multi-stage value chain: incubation → fry production → commercial fish farming → processing → compound feed production → trade. Such a complex structure requires the systematic organization of management accounting and internal control.

In international practice, the methodology of management accounting for such structures has been developed by Kaplan and Atkinson [5], as well as Horngren et al. [6]. Local scholars, including Alikulov A. I. [7] and Khasanov B. A. [8], have developed the theoretical foundations of management accounting, while Fayzullaev N. K. and Rasulov B. S. [15] examined the issues of organizing management accounting in cluster-type enterprises.

However, key elements of management accounting, such as transfer pricing, segment reporting, and internal control systems, have not yet been fully established in the fishery clusters of Uzbekistan. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to scientifically substantiate the priority directions for organizing management accounting and internal control systems in fishery clusters and to develop practical recommendations for their implementation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the theory and practice of management accounting, Kaplan and Atkinson [5] established modern management accounting as a strategic management tool and highlighted the complex nature of cost accounting in cluster structures. Horngren et al. [6] developed a methodology for the comprehensive application of transfer pricing and segmental analysis in cost accounting. In her textbook on management accounting, Vahrushina M. A. [9] described in detail the principles of forming internal accounting policies for multi-unit structures.

In his foundational article, Hirshleifer J. [14] was among the first scholars to analyse the economic basis of transfer pricing. The OECD Guidelines [12] regulate transfer pricing methods for multinational enterprises and define methodological approaches to the cost-plus method, including its application in agricultural activities. Selan B. and Aliqulov A. [16] proposed an approach to transfer pricing in fishery clusters adapted to local conditions.

In the international literature on segment reporting and IFRS 8, the methodology for identifying operating segments based on the “management approach” has been extensively studied [11]. In the field of internal control systems, the COSO Framework [13] is applied as a widely recognised standard and defines the principles of internal control based on five interrelated components.

In local literature, Alikulov A. I. [7] addressed theoretical and practical issues of cost accounting and proposed specific methodological approaches for agricultural enterprises. In their textbook on management accounting, Khasanov B. A. and Khoshimov A. A. [8] outlined the fundamentals of developing internal accounting policies within the context of Uzbekistan.

Overall, the analysis of the existing scientific literature shows that a comprehensive methodology for organizing management accounting and internal control systems in fishery clusters has not yet been fully developed for the conditions of Uzbekistan. Therefore, this research is aimed at filling this scientific gap.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed scientific methods of analysis and synthesis. In particular, systematic analysis, comparative analysis, modelling, and a normative-methodological approach were used. The object of the research is the fishery clusters within the “O‘zbekbaliqsanoat” Association, while the subject of the research is the methodological and practical issues of establishing management accounting and internal control systems in these clusters.

Primary data were collected from the financial and economic activity reports of five clusters that are members of the “O‘zbekbaliqsanoat” Association for 2019–2024 [2]. Secondary data were obtained from official sources of the Statistics Agency [1], international standards, including IFRS 8 and the COSO Framework, as well as scientific literature.

The methodological framework consists of three components: (1) the stages of formulating the management accounting policy; (2) a transfer pricing model; and (3) a segment reporting form compliant with IFRS 8 [11]. The COSO Internal Control — Integrated Framework [13] was applied as the primary methodological basis for designing the internal control system. The formulation of the management accounting policy was structured as a five-stage process, taking into account the requirements of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting” [4].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The current state of management accounting and internal control systems in Uzbekistan's fishery clusters reveals a number of systemic issues. The multi-link value chain of fishery clusters — incubation → fry production → commercial fish farming → processing → compound feed production → sales — requires specific management accounting solutions for each stage. For this purpose, methodological solutions were developed in three main areas.

First area: formulation of the management accounting policy. The management accounting policy is a crucial internal document that establishes the procedures and principles of management accounting within a cluster. Unlike the financial accounting policy, it defines the internal accounting and reporting procedures required for managerial decision-making [7; 8]. The formulation of the management accounting policy includes five stages:

- Grouping the factors that influence the accounting policy, including industry characteristics, scale of activity, operating segments, and external requirements;
- Defining principles and methods, including the cost calculation method and allocation base;
- Preparing a draft accounting policy within the management accounting system;
- Discussing and formalizing the draft;
- Approving and implementing the policy by the Cluster Council.

Second area: transfer pricing formation. A transfer price is an internal price applied when one division of a cluster transfers or sells its products to another division [14]. In international practice, three main methods are used to establish transfer prices: cost-based, market-based, and negotiated methods [12]. For fishery clusters, a hybrid model is proposed: for products with an active market, such as finished feed and filleted fish, the market price method should be applied; for products without an active market, such as larvae and fry, the cost-plus method with a 15–25% profitability margin is recommended. This range corresponds to the median indicators for agricultural sectors recommended under the cost-plus method in the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines [12] and is consistent with the research of Selan B. and Alikulov A. [16].

Third area: segment reporting format. IFRS 8 "Operating Segments" requires large enterprises and clusters to prepare separate reports for each operating segment [11]. The standard defines operating segments based on the "management approach". For fishery clusters, five main operating segments have been identified: (1) fish farming; (2) processing; (3) compound feed production; (4) sales; and (5) other activities.

A sample segment reporting format for these segments is presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Segmental Reporting Format for a Fishery Cluster (sample, in million UZS)

Indicator	Farming	Processing	Feed	Sales	Other	Elim.	Total
Revenue from external customers	0	0	0	1,500	120	0	1,620
Inter-segment (transfer)	800	200	400	0	0	-1,400	0
Total revenue	800	200	400	1,500	120	-1,400	1,620
Production costs	550	150	320	0	80	0	1,100
Inter-segment costs	0	0	0	1,400	0	-1,400	0
Segment profit	250	50	80	-50	40	0	370
Segment assets	1,200	350	450	200	100	0	2,300

Note: The "Elim." column represents the elimination of inter-segment transactions, in accordance with the requirements of IFRS 8.

Source: Developed by the author based on practical data from the "Uzbekbaliqsanoat" (Uzbekistan Fishery Industry) Association.[2; 11]

As shown in Table 1, inter-segment transfer turnover amounting to UZS 1,400 million is eliminated from the consolidated total through the "Elim." column. This approach complies with IFRS 8 requirements and reflects the cluster's actual transactions with external customers.

Although the sales segment shows a negative segment profit of UZS 50 million, this indicates that transfer prices for deliveries to other segments may be understated. This situation should therefore be carefully considered when making management decisions.

The internal control system was designed based on the COSO Framework (Table 2).

Table 2
Components of the Internal Control System in the Fishery Cluster

Component	Fishery-Specific Characteristics	Implementation Measures
Control Environment	Cluster's code of ethics and employee qualification requirements	Approval of the code of ethics, professional development courses
Risk Assessment	Biological risks (diseases), market risks	Creating a risk matrix and updating it twice a year
Control Activities	Feed consumption limits, pond parameters, FCR control	Daily monitoring logs, delegation of authority
Information & Communication	Pond–management–cluster information system	ERP system implementation, weekly reports
Monitoring Activities	Auditing the movement of biological assets, feed consumption, and transfer prices	Quarterly and annual internal audit service

Source: Developed by the author based on the COSO Internal Control — Integrated Framework.[13]

The COSO-based internal control system presented in Table 2 has been adapted to reflect the specific characteristics of fishery clusters. These include control over the movement of biological assets, such as fish quantity, mortality, and survival rate; control over feed consumption and warehouse operations, including the FCR coefficient and the risk of misappropriation; and monitoring of water quality and basin parameters. Although such a system is widely used in international practice, it has not yet been systematically applied in local practice [13; 15].

It should also be noted that, in the segment report, the negative profit of the sales segment, amounting to UZS 50 million, and the high profit of the fish farming segment, amounting to UZS 250 million, may indicate that transfer prices have been set incorrectly. This situation highlights the need to conduct a transfer pricing audit for managerial decision-making, a point also emphasized by Selan B. and Alikulov A. [16].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study identifies the priority directions for organizing management accounting and internal control systems in fishery clusters. Table 1 presents a segment reporting format, while Table 2 provides a practical model of an internal control system based on the COSO Framework. The research findings create a systematic foundation for improving management accounting practices in the fishery clusters of Uzbekistan.

Based on the research findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

For fishery clusters, the formulation of the management accounting policy is a five-stage process developed with consideration of the industry's multi-link structure, seasonality, and biological risks.

The mixed transfer pricing model is based on two principles: for products with an active market, such as finished feed and sliced fish, the market price method is applied; for products without an active market, such as larvae and fry, the cost-plus model with a 15–25% margin is used. This range is consistent with the OECD Guidelines [12].

A segment reporting format compliant with IFRS 8 requirements has been developed for five operating segments: fish farming, processing, compound feed production, sales, and other activities. Inter-segment turnover is eliminated through the "Elim." column, ensuring that the consolidated final result is accurately reflected.

Based on the COSO Framework [13], five components of the internal control system for fishery clusters — the control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring — have been adapted to the specific features of the fishery industry.

Based on the above conclusions, the following scientific and practical recommendations are proposed:

First, the "O'zbekbaliqsanoat" Association and the Ministry of Economy and Finance should jointly develop and standardize a model management accounting policy specifically designed for fishery clusters across the industry.

Second, the transfer pricing model should be empirically tested in pilot clusters, such as A-Cluster and B-Cluster, and the 15–25% margin range should be refined by adapting it to local economic conditions.

Third, the implementation of segment reporting in accordance with IFRS 8 should begin with large clusters in order to ensure financial transparency for foreign investors.

Fourth, the COSO-based internal control system should be integrated with ERP systems, IoT sensors, and artificial intelligence technologies, particularly for real-time monitoring of feed consumption and biological asset movements.

The research findings may be implemented by the “O‘zbekbaliqsanoat” Association, the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the National Association of Accountants and Auditors. Future research directions include the integration of digital technologies, such as ERP, IoT, and AI, the incorporation of ESG indicators into segment reporting, and the empirical evaluation of pilot projects.

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